

Policy-Driven Access-Edge Enforcement for DOCSIS Upstream in HFC Networks

Ivan Ivanets, Volodymyr Ovsyak, Oleksandr Ovsyak, and Andrzej Kułakowski

Abstract—Hybrid fiber-coaxial (HFC) access networks based on DOCSIS continue to serve a large broadband footprint, yet upstream service quality under contention is often dominated by latency-under-load and jitter rather than peak throughput. This article presents an intermediate modernization step that treats transport-facing upstream behavior as a software-defined, policy-managed function enforced at the access edge, without changes to the coaxial plant, DOCSIS PHY/MAC, or customer premises equipment. The proposed edge node classifies traffic using operator-controlled DSCP markings and applies per-class actions using VPP dataplane primitives, including deterministic policing and controlled degradation via remark-then-drop. We evaluate two minimal policies: (i) a fixed-rate bulk cap that preserves an interactive protected class under contention, and (ii) a two-rate envelope that demotes excess bulk traffic via DSCP remarking before dropping above an excess threshold. The methodology emphasizes operational verifiability: policy effects are observed through per-class throughput and stability indicators and corroborated using policer statistics and post-policy DSCP accounting. Initial controlled experiments on a two-node bare-metal testbed demonstrate enforceable bulk caps and an observable demotion stage preceding drops, supporting implementation feasibility and measurable policy effects under contention in a constrained validation environment.

Index Terms— HFC, DOCSIS, access-edge enforcement, DiffServ, policy enforcement, programmable data planes, VPP.

I. INTRODUCTION

HYBRID fiber-coaxial (HFC) DOCSIS-based cable access networks remain a major component of fixed broadband infrastructure, with DOCSIS 3.1 available to about one third of European Union households by mid-2023 (33.6%) and deployed to United States census blocks containing approximately 78% of households [1], [2]. At the

same time, the application mix increasingly emphasizes interactive and real-time services (e.g., video conferencing and gaming), for which quality of experience is dominated by baseline latency, jitter, and latency-under-load rather than headline throughput [3]. This shifts the operational problem from maximizing peak capacity to ensuring explicit and verifiable per-class upstream behavior under contention—an area where best-effort dynamics can blur operator intent and make outcomes difficult to audit.

A central reason is that HFC upstream behavior is constrained not only by spectrum allocation and noise susceptibility, but also by the request–grant nature of DOCSIS scheduling and its sensitivity to delay. At the architectural level, cable networks have modernized rapidly—by mid-2023, more than four fifths (81.3%) of DOCSIS 3.0 networks in the EU had been upgraded to DOCSIS 3.1—while simultaneously shifting key functions and pushing the physical layer closer to subscribers via Remote PHY Devices (RPDs) [1], [4]. Large-scale operational deployments of RPDs underscore the practicality of this distributed access evolution [5]. Under heavy contention, however, the separation between upstream scheduling/buffering and transport feedback loops can amplify latency under load and degrade per-flow responsiveness—effects that motivate active queue management (AQM) guidance in DOCSIS deployments [6].

Meanwhile, full physical modernization—either by upgrading the outside plant toward DOCSIS 4.0 or by migrating to fiber-to-the-home (FTTH)—is often constrained by capital cost, rollout logistics, and long deployment cycles. DOCSIS 4.0 expands the upstream roadmap through Full Duplex DOCSIS and Extended Spectrum DOCSIS modes, but these gains typically require coordinated upgrades across the access domain and careful plant readiness, which can slow time-to-benefit at scale [7]. Operators therefore need intermediate options that improve upstream service quality without changing the coaxial plant or subscriber equipment, and that can be introduced incrementally with measurable, auditable outcomes.

This article argues that a practical intermediate step is to treat upstream transport-facing behavior as a software-defined, policy-managed function enforced at the access edge. We present a policy-driven architecture in which an edge node co-located with the access domain classifies traffic using operator-controlled markings (e.g., the Differentiated Services Code Point, DSCP) and enforces per-class actions using VPP dataplane primitives, including deterministic policing and controlled degradation via remark-then-drop, while remaining compatible with DOCSIS-based access and existing customer

I. Ivanets is with the Department of Computer Technologies in Publishing and Printing, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine (e-mail: ivan.d.ivanets@lpnu.ua).

V. Ovsyak is with the Department of Computer Technologies in Publishing and Printing, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine, and also with the Department of Applied Informatics, Kielce University of Technology, Kielce, Poland (e-mail: vovsyak@ukr.net; vovsyak@tu.kielce.pl).

O. Ovsyak is with the Department of Computer Science, Ukrainian National Forestry University, Lviv, Ukraine (e-mail: ovsjak@nltu.edu.ua).

A. Kułakowski is with the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Automatic Control and Computer Science, Kielce University of Technology, Kielce, Poland (e-mail: mssak@tu.kielce.pl).

Supplemental material (reproducibility artifact) is available via Code Ocean (doi: 10.24433/CO.0628266.v1).

This work has been submitted to the IEEE for possible publication. Copyright may be transferred without notice, after which this version may no longer be accessible.

premises equipment (CPE) [8]. The approach leverages Vector Packet Processor (VPP), a mature high-speed software dataplane framework based on a graph processing model and vectorized packet processing, to realize deployable per-class enforcement at the access edge [9]. The policy workflow (definition–deployment–verification) is operationalized as versioned artifacts and assessed through testbed-based experiments aligned with CI-style validation practices using FD.io CSIT reporting [10].

To make the contribution concrete and actionable for practitioners, this article provides:

- 1) A policy-driven access-edge enforcement model for DOCSIS upstream that maps DSCP classes to explicit per-class semantics under contention, including deterministic bulk caps and controlled degradation, while preserving compatibility with existing DOCSIS access infrastructure and CPE.
- 2) A VPP-based implementation blueprint for ingress classification and per-class enforcement at the access edge, including the expression of policies as versioned configuration artifacts and the exposure of evidence signals for auditability.
- 3) A reproducible controlled-validation workflow that links per-class service behavior to dataplane evidence in an HFC-like contention environment.

The remainder of the article summarizes the relevant HFC/DOCSIS context, details the policy model and access-edge enforcement architecture, and then reports representative results that illustrate the operational value of policy-driven upstream behavior in contention scenarios.

II. BACKGROUND AND POSITIONING

A. Why HFC Upstream Degrades Under Contention

HFC upstream is a shared, scheduled medium: upstream capacity is limited, and transmissions are coordinated through DOCSIS request–grant scheduling and OFDMA resource allocation [11], [12]. Under contention, scheduling cycles and queue growth translate into latency under load and jitter—performance dimensions that dominate user experience for interactive services [3]. Controlling queuing delay and stabilizing per-class behavior therefore become operational priorities; DOCSIS AQM requirements and guidance target exactly these effects [13], [6].

B. Modernization Trends: Distributed Access and Centralized Control

Operators extend the coaxial plant using distributed access architectures (DAA), including Remote PHY (R-PHY), which move DOCSIS physical-layer functions closer to subscribers while retaining centralized MAC and higher-layer functions in a virtualized CMTS/CCAP core [4]. Large-scale deployments demonstrate the practicality of this shift [5]. However, upstream contention occurs at the access edge, while many control and policy decisions remain centralized—an architectural trade-off that becomes particularly visible when upstream performance is delay-sensitive.

DOCSIS 4.0 expands the upstream roadmap through Full Duplex and Extended Spectrum modes, but realizing these gains typically requires coordinated upgrades and careful plant readiness, which can delay time-to-benefit at scale [7]. Fig. 1 positions these paths and highlights why intermediate, software-driven improvements remain valuable in many operational contexts.

Fig. 1. Positioning of the proposed policy-driven access-edge enforcement within a DAA/RPD deployment: centralized policy/operations and vCMTS/CCAP functions remain in the headend/core, while a VPP-based edge node enforces DSCP-based per-class semantics at the upstream contention point and exposes dataplane evidence (policer counters and DSCP accounting) for verifiable operation.

C. What Prior Work Solves, and What It Leaves Open

Existing paths largely improve either capacity (DOCSIS 4.0, FTTH) or physical-layer placement (DAA/RPD), but they do not inherently provide explicit, verifiable per-class policy semantics at the access edge (Fig. 1) [4], [5], [7]. In parallel, programmable data planes have matured: FD.io VPP enables classification and enforcement functions to be implemented as high-performance packet-processing pipelines on commodity hardware [9]. This creates an alternative design point for upstream control: express class behavior explicitly as policy and enforce it where contention occurs.

D. Positioning of This Work: Policy-Driven Edge Transport Control

This article frames upstream modernization as a policy and operations problem. We introduce a policy-driven edge node that classifies traffic using operator-controlled DiffServ codepoints (DSCP) carried in the IP header and enforces per-class actions in the data plane [8]. In our evaluation, DSCP EF denotes an interactive/protected aggregate, while CS0 denotes default best-effort bulk traffic. The evaluated policies differ in how the bulk class is conditioned under contention: Policy A applies a deterministic cap, whereas Policy B applies two-rate, three-color metering (trTCM) with progressive demotion (CS0→CS1 remarking) and drop above the excess rate (EIR) [14]. Table I summarizes the minimal policy semantics evaluated in this work and the observable outcomes expected under contention. In our implementation, each policy is realized as a VPP CLI configuration script persisted as a file and referenced from the VPP startup configuration; CSIT generates these configuration files during VPP initialization and applies them at test setup, enabling repeatable

benchmarking, regression tracking, and auditable policy validation [10].

TABLE I

MINIMAL POLICY SEMANTICS EVALUATED IN THIS WORK

Aspect	Policy A Deterministic cap	Policy B Graceful degradation
Examples	EF: interactive; CS0 bulk (hard cap).	EF: interactive; CS0 bulk (remark→drop).
Classifier (input)	EF→Interactive, CS0→Bulk.	Same (controls for classifier).
Intent	Protect EF via a hard ceiling on CS0.	Protect EF while CS0 degrades progressively.
Access-Edge enforcement (VPP)	EF: not rate-limited in this work. CS0: single-rate policer.	EF: same. CS0: RFC 2698 trTCM: ≤CIR pass; CIR→EIR remark CS0→CS1; >EIR drop.
Observable evidence	EF latency/jitter stable; CS0 goodput plateaus; policer/drop counters.	trTCM color counters (G/Y/R); CS0/CS1 mix; drops mainly above EIR; progressive degradation behavior.

Note: Policy B uses RFC 2698 trTCM with two thresholds (CIR, EIR): CS0 is forwarded up to CIR, remarked to CS1 between CIR and EIR, and dropped above the excess rate, yielding progressive degradation.

The contribution is not a new queuing or scheduling algorithm; rather, it is a deployable HFC-oriented access-edge enforcement architecture that makes upstream class behavior explicit, auditable, and reproducible.

III. ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

Section III summarizes the proposed architecture as two planes: a centralized policy/assurance plane and an access-edge enforcement node. Policies are versioned as deployable artifacts, pushed to the edge for per-class enforcement, while verification consumes dataplane evidence (counters, DSCP accounting, per-class KPIs) to gate promotion and enable rollback.

A. Design Goal: Verifiable Per-Class Upstream Behavior at the Access Edge

The goal is to improve upstream service quality in DOCSIS-based HFC networks by making transport-facing behavior policy-managed and edge-enforced—specifically via per-class rate caps for bulk uploads, protected-class stability under contention (e.g., interactive flows), and controlled degradation (remark-then-drop)—without changing the coaxial plant or CPE. The system assumes DOCSIS PHY/MAC operation remains standards-compliant, while modernization is introduced as a software layer in the access domain. This makes the approach practical as an intermediate step when DOCSIS 4.0 upgrades or FTTH migration are not immediately feasible [7].

B. Deployment Assumptions and Trust Boundary

Figure 2 summarizes the two-plane architecture: a centralized policy and assurance plane and an access-edge

enforcement node placed close to the upstream contention point. Policies are produced as versioned artifacts and deployed to the edge, while verification consumes dataplane evidence returned from the edge to gate promotion and enable deterministic rollback.

Fig. 2. Closed-loop policy-driven access-edge enforcement architecture.

Figure 2 also clarifies the functional role of each block in the closed-loop workflow. Operator intent is first expressed as per-class service semantics and encoded as a versioned policy artifact in the policy controller/repository. This artifact is then delivered through a controlled deployment path to the access-edge enforcement node, where DSCP-based classification and VPP enforcement primitives translate the selected policy into concrete dataplane behavior close to the upstream contention point. In parallel, the evidence path collects policer statistics, DSCP accounting, and service-level measurements, linking observed outcomes to the active policy revision. These signals are finally consumed by the CI workflow and KPI/evidence checks to support validation gating, auditable promotion, and deterministic rollback.

The policy and assurance plane expresses operator intent as explicit class definitions and behaviors (e.g., “protect interactive traffic under contention”, “cap bulk uploads”), versions them as deployable artifacts, and integrates them into a change workflow with auditability and rollback. The deployment interface is therefore a controlled distribution channel from the policy controller/repository to the access edge, ensuring that the same policy revision used in validation is the one enforced in production.

The access-edge enforcement node implements classification and per-class enforcement using VPP primitives. Traffic is mapped to classes using stable, operator-controlled inputs such as DSCP, and then processed according to policy using policing (fixed-rate caps) and controlled degradation (remark-then-drop), making outcomes explicit and measurable rather than emergent under best-effort contention. The evidence interface exposes enforcement causality and service impact via policer counters, DSCP remark accounting, and per-class throughput/latency measurements, which are consumed by CI-style verification (e.g., CSIT reporting). The policy semantics and verification signals are summarized in Table I. DSCP is treated as an operator-domain signal:

classification is enforced at the access edge, and remarking/policing ensures that untrusted endpoints cannot obtain priority service by self-marking.

C. Policy Lifecycle and Assurance Loop (Softwarization & Management)

The proposed mechanism is operationalized as a policy artifact with explicit, testable semantics rather than an ad-hoc device configuration. Operator intent is expressed as a versioned policy definition (class match + enforcement action + parameters), reviewed and promoted through a change workflow. Each policy revision is validated in a CI-style pipeline against a fixed run matrix (baseline vs. Policy A/B) and acceptance thresholds defined on service KPIs (e.g., EF tail latency under load and bulk goodput caps). Enforcement causality is verified using dataplane evidence: policer counters, DSCP remark accounting, and per-class throughput/latency measurements, enabling auditability and regression detection. Once promoted, the same artifact is deployed to the access edge and can be rolled back deterministically if KPI regression is detected. This closes the loop between intent, enforcement, and assurance, aligning packet processing softwarization (VPP primitives) with network management practices (versioning, gating, and verification).

IV. VPP-BASED ACCESS-EDGE ENFORCEMENT: PIPELINE, POLICIES, AND DEPLOYMENT

A. Enforcement Pipeline: Ingress Classification, Policy Selection, and Verifiable Actions

At the access edge, packets traverse a deterministic enforcement pipeline that makes per-class behavior explicit and measurable under upstream contention. The processing stages are:

- 1) **Ingress and trusted classification signals**
Traffic arrives on the uplink-facing ingress of the edge node. Packets are assigned to a service class using operator-controlled signals (e.g., DSCP), establishing a stable mapping between flows and policy classes.
- 2) **Policy selection per class (artifact-defined semantics)**
The classifier output selects a class-specific policy instance (e.g., Policy A for protected-class stability and bulk caps; Policy B for controlled degradation), with all parameters defined by the versioned policy artifact.
- 3) **Per-class enforcement primitives**
The selected policy applies VPP enforcement actions such as fixed-rate policing for deterministic caps and controlled degradation via remark-then-drop for tunable service reduction under overload.
- 4) **Forwarding and service continuity**
Packets that pass enforcement are forwarded along the normal datapath without requiring changes to DOCSIS PHY/MAC behavior or customer equipment.
- 5) **Evidence export for causality and assurance**
Enforcement outcomes are exposed as dataplane evidence—policer counters, DSCP remark accounting, and per-class throughput/latency measurements—

enabling CI-based verification (CSIT) and auditability of policy behavior.

B. Policy semantics (Policy A and Policy B)

Policy A (deterministic cap for bulk). The bulk class (DSCP CS0) is enforced by a single-rate policer configured with a fixed cap $R_CS0_cap = 1$ Gbit/s. The protected class (DSCP EF) bypasses the cap (or uses a non-binding limit). Under load, the expected outcome is straightforward: CS0 throughput saturates near the configured cap while EF remains stable.

Policy B (graceful degradation for bulk). The bulk class (CS0) is enforced using two-rate behavior with CIR = 1 Gbit/s and EIR = 2 Gbit/s. Traffic between CIR and EIR is demoted by remarking CS0→CS1; traffic above EIR is dropped. This policy produces a tunable “degradation envelope” in which overload first results in demotion (observable via DSCP distribution counters) before drops dominate.

Both policies are intentionally small: they can be explained in a few lines, audited via counters, and validated in controlled contention scenarios without changes to DOCSIS PHY/MAC or customer equipment.

C. Policy-as-artifact deployment and observability

To support repeatability, each policy is packaged as a versioned CLI configuration artifact applied at boot. A policy file (e.g., *policy_a.cli*, *policy_b.cli*) contains the complete set of VPP commands that instantiate the classifier and the policer/remark chain. The DUT startup configuration executes exactly one such file at boot, removing any dependence on interactive CLI steps during experiments and matching operational practice (promotion/rollback by swapping artifacts).

Enforcement is verified using two complementary evidence paths:

- policer statistics: per-policy counters for conform/exceed/violate (or equivalent) bytes/packets and drop counts, directly linking observed outcomes to enforcement;
- DSCP distribution counters on egress: used in Policy B to confirm that overload triggers demotion (CS0→CS1) prior to drops.

V. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY: CONTROLLED BARE-METAL VALIDATION

A. Testbed roles and topology

The evaluation uses a fixed two-node bare-metal setup interconnected by a dedicated high-speed Ethernet link (Fig. 3) to isolate policy effects from virtualization artifacts. Both nodes execute iperf3 over VPP HostStack using LD_PRELOAD. DUT1 acts as the traffic source and additionally runs a lightweight, HostStack-based uplink conditioning stage in user space to reproduce DOCSIS-like upstream conditions without relying on Linux traffic control. Specifically, this conditioning stage provides: (i) a bottleneck service rate, (ii) periodic service opportunities with grant-cycle-like timing variability, (iii) burst shaping within the conditioning stage to induce upstream-like burstiness, and (iv) a configurable queue discipline with AQM-like behavior. The

intent is not to model DOCSIS PHY/MAC, but to provide an HFC/DOCSIS-like upstream impairment environment in which edge policies can be evaluated under repeatable contention. The conditioning was sanity-checked via coarse-grained A/B comparisons against an ns-3 DOCSIS simulation to align rate and latency-under-load trends at the system level.

DUT2 hosts the enforcement point: it runs VPP and applies the proposed DSCP-based policy pipeline on the uplink-facing DPDK ingress interface, while the iperf3 server runs over HostStack. A separate management interface provides SSH connectivity from the CI orchestrator (FD.io CSIT) to both nodes.

Fig. 3. Two-node bare-metal testbed and roles. DUT1 generates EF/CS0 traffic using iperf3 over VPP HostStack (via LD_PRELOAD) and applies user-space uplink conditioning to reproduce DOCSIS-like upstream effects. DUT2 runs the iperf3 server over HostStack and enforces DSCP-based policies on the uplink-facing DPDK ingress interface under CI orchestration (FD.io CSIT).

B. Traffic model: one server port, two DSCP classes, controlled contention

Each run lasts 30 seconds and uses a single iperf3 server port on DUT2 for all flows (iperf3 default port is used unless otherwise configured). Two DSCP-marked traffic classes share this same server port to ensure that class selection is driven by DSCP rather than by port-based separation:

- protected class: DSCP = EF, target rate 200 Mbit/s;
- bulk class: DSCP = CS0, aggregate target demand 5 Gbit/s generated using 10 parallel TCP streams.

The bulk target demand intentionally exceeds the enforced thresholds to trigger Policy A caps and Policy B CIR/EIR behavior, while the EF rate is chosen to be clearly observable yet non-dominant relative to the bulk load. Because both classes share one server port, DSCP remains the sole class selector for the enforcement stage described next.

C. Enforcement placement: input DPDK interface on DUT2

All enforcement is applied on the input DPDK interface of DUT2 before packets are delivered to the HostStack socket path and the iperf3 server process. Packets are first classified using DSCP and the fixed destination port, then mapped to an enforcement profile (Policy A or Policy B). This placement ensures that observed effects are attributable to the edge dataplane pipeline rather than to application-layer behavior. Accordingly, policer and post-policy DSCP counters collected on DUT2 provide direct causal evidence for the per-class throughput outcomes reported in Section V.E.

D. Run matrix

To keep verification interpretable, the run matrix contains three configurations executed under identical topology, duration, and traffic parameters:

- baseline: no class-based enforcement enabled;
- Policy A: CS0 enforced by a deterministic cap (default in this work: 1 Gbit/s); EF is non-binding;
- Policy B: CS0 enforced by two-rate behavior with CIR = 1 Gbit/s and EIR = 2 Gbit/s, with CS0→CS1 remarking for “yellow” traffic and drops for “red” traffic; EF is non-binding.

Each configuration is repeated multiple times to confirm run-to-run stability under the same fixed hardware environment.

E. Metrics and evidence collection

For each run-matrix configuration, the methodology separates operator-visible outcomes from dataplane evidence to avoid ambiguous interpretations.

1) Operator-visible outcomes (iperf3)

For each DSCP-marked flow group, we record achieved throughput over the 30-second interval. The expected outcomes are: (i) EF throughput remains stable across configurations, and (ii) CS0 delivered throughput reflects the configured cap (Policy A) or the delivered degradation envelope (Policy B).

2) Dataplane evidence (VPP counters on DUT2)

- a) Policer counters: conform/exceed/violate bytes and packets (and drops where applicable), providing causal evidence that enforcement decisions explain the observed throughput outcomes.
- b) Post-policy DSCP distribution counters on DUT2 egress: used to validate class behavior in the VPP pipeline. In Policy B, a non-zero CS1 delta for the bulk class confirms the demotion stage (CS0→CS1) prior to drops.

This evidence structure links measured throughput directly to policer behavior and to post-policy DSCP accounting in the enforcement pipeline.

F. Automation and reproducibility artifacts

Policies are deployed as boot-time configuration artifacts, ensuring deterministic setup without interactive CLI steps. Each run produces a compact evidence package consisting of iperf3 JSON outputs and VPP counter snapshots (before/after), enabling automated post-processing and stable comparisons across configurations. The overall workflow aligns with CI-style methodology and is integrated with the FD.io CSIT orchestration/reporting pipeline; a dedicated reproducibility artifact is also prepared for external validation [15].

VI. RESULTS

A. Validation scope and reporting protocol

This section reports a controlled validation of the proposed policy-driven access-edge mechanism, focusing on (i) directional service effects under contention summarized as

normalized KPIs (Fig. 4) and (ii) enforcement causality confirmed by dataplane evidence. The experiments follow the topology, traffic model, and run matrix defined in Section V.

Fig. 4. Normalized KPI summary under contention (higher is better): CS0 bulk goodput, inverse-normalized EF tail latency (P95), and inverse-normalized EF jitter for Baseline, Policy A, and Policy B. Values are normalized per metric relative to the best observed value across configurations in the current run set.

B. Directional service effects under contention

Under Baseline operation, bulk uploads competing at the upstream bottleneck degrade protected-class service, resulting in higher tail latency and increased variability for interactive flows. Enabling Policy A makes bulk behavior deterministic by enforcing an explicit cap on the bulk class while improving protected-class stability under the same offered load. Enabling Policy B produces a controlled degradation envelope: bulk traffic is first demoted (remarked) and subsequently dropped once thresholds are exceeded, reducing contention pressure and preserving protected-class stability at the cost of bulk delivery efficiency. These observations are consistent with the stated goal of making per-class upstream behavior explicit, policy-managed, and verifiable at the access edge rather than emergent under best-effort contention.

C. Enforcement causality confirmed by dataplane evidence

To ensure that the observed trends are attributable to the enforcement pipeline (Section IV), we verify causality using dataplane evidence exported by the edge node. Under Policy A, policer counters reflect sustained token-bucket enforcement for the bulk class at the configured rate, consistent with the intended deterministic cap semantics. Under Policy B, DSCP accounting confirms bulk demotion preceding drops, and meter/policer statistics together with drop counters evolve consistently with the configured CIR/EIR envelope, providing dataplane evidence for the controlled reduction in bulk delivery under overload. Together, policer counters, DSCP remark accounting, and per-class measurements instantiate the closed-loop assurance workflow shown in Fig. 2 and support CI-style validation (e.g., CSIT reporting).

D. Limitations

The present validation has several important limitations. First, the evaluation is conducted on a fixed two-node bare-metal setup, which is sufficient for controlled proof-of-concept testing but does not represent a larger operator-scale deployment. Second, the uplink conditioning stage is designed to reproduce DOCSIS-like upstream impairment effects at the system level rather than to implement a full DOCSIS

PHY/MAC model. Third, the current results are limited to controlled short-duration experiments intended to demonstrate directional policy effects under contention. Finally, the present study does not include comparative evaluation against active queue management schemes, scheduler-based approaches, or operator-deployed DOCSIS mechanisms. These limitations define the scope of the current manuscript and should be taken into account when interpreting the reported results.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This article presents a practical intermediate modernization step for DOCSIS upstream in HFC networks: software-defined, policy-driven per-class enforcement at the access edge using DSCP-based classification and VPP policer primitives. The proposed approach translates operator intent into explicit and auditable behavior under contention without requiring changes to the coaxial plant, DOCSIS PHY/MAC, or customer premises equipment.

Using a fixed two-node bare-metal setup and a controlled, reproducible validation methodology, the current results show that protected-class (EF) delivery remains stable under contention while bulk traffic (CS0) becomes operationally predictable. Policy A enforces a deterministic bulk service envelope aligned with the configured cap (≈ 1 Gbit/s). Policy B provides a two-rate behavior in which excess traffic is first remarked (CS0 \rightarrow CS1) and then dropped when exceeding the defined envelope, enabling a controlled trade-off between bulk utilization and protected-class tail stability.

The reported outcomes are supported not only by throughput measurements but also by dataplane evidence from DUT2. Policer conform/exceed/violate counters and post-policy DSCP distribution confirm that the observed per-class behavior is produced by the intended enforcement pipeline rather than by application-layer artifacts. The normalized KPI view further illustrates the expected directional effect on tail latency (P95) and jitter under contention.

Overall, the work demonstrates the feasibility of a policy-driven access-edge enforcement architecture for controlled upstream behavior in HFC networks within a constrained validation environment. The present results support implementation feasibility and motivate broader comparative and larger-scale evaluation in future work.

REFERENCES

- [1] European Commission, “Digital Decade 2024: Broadband Coverage in Europe 2023,” Jul. 2024. Accessed: Jan. 22, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/digital-decade-2024-broadband-coverage-europe-2023>
- [2] Federal Communications Commission, “2022 Communications Marketplace Report,” Washington, DC, USA, Rep. FCC 22-103, Dec. 30, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.fcc.gov/public/attachments/FCC-22-103A1.pdf>
- [3] Broadband Internet Technical Advisory Group, “Latency Explained,” Jan. 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www.bitag.org/documents/BITAG_latency_explained.pdf
- [4] Cable Television Laboratories, Inc., “Remote PHY Specification,” CM-SP-R-PHYv02.0-118-230512, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cablelabs.com/specifications/CM-SP-R-PHY>
- [5] J. Salinger and S. Sigman, “Lessons from Operating Tens of Thousands of Remote PHY Devices,” in Proc. SCTE Cable-Tec Expo, Atlanta, GA, USA, Oct. 2021. Accessed: Jan. 22, 2026. [Online]. Available:

- <https://nctatechnicalpapers.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/2021-lessons-from-operating-tens-of-thousands-of-remote-phy-devices.pdf>
- [6] B. Wyrowski, K. Nichols, and R. Pan, "Active Queue Management in DOCSIS 3.1 Networks: A Practical Deployment Perspective," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 145–151, Mar. 2015.
- [7] Cable Television Laboratories, Inc., "DOCSIS® 4.0 Physical Layer Specification," CM-SP-PHYv4.0-103-201202, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cablelabs.com/specifications/CM-SP-PHYv4.0>
- [8] K. Nichols, S. Blake, F. Baker, and D. Black, "Definition of the Differentiated Services Field (DS Field) in the IPv4 and IPv6 Headers," RFC 2474, Dec. 1998. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc2474.html>
- [9] D. Barach, L. Linguaglossa, D. Marion, P. Pfister, S. Pontarelli, and D. Rossi, "High-Speed Software Data Plane via Vectorized Packet Processing," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 56, no. 12, pp. 97–103, Dec. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://nonsns.github.io/paper/rossi18commag.pdf>
- [10] FD.io, "CSIT Report (csit_master.pdf)," Mar. 2023. Accessed: Jan. 22, 2026. [Online]. Available: https://docs.fd.io/csit/master/report/_static/archive/csit_master.pdf
- [11] Cable Television Laboratories, Inc., "DOCSIS® 3.1 Physical Layer Specification," CM-SP-PHYv3.1. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cablelabs.com/specifications/CM-SP-PHYv3.1>
- [12] Cable Television Laboratories, Inc., "DOCSIS® 3.1 MAC and Upper Layer Protocols Interface (MULPI) Specification," CM-SP-MULPIv3.1. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cablelabs.com/specifications/CM-SP-MULPIv3.1>
- [13] G. White, R. Pan, and K. Nichols, "Active Queue Management Requirements for DOCSIS Cable Modems," RFC 8034, Feb. 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc8034.html>
- [14] J. Heinanen and R. Guerin, "A Two Rate Three Color Marker," RFC 2698, Sep. 1999. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc2698.html>
- [15] I. Ivanets, 2026, "Reproducibility artifact for 'Policy-Driven Edge Enforcement for DOCSIS Upstream in HFC Networks' (Version v1)," Code Ocean, doi: 10.24433/CO.0628266.v1.